

A New Atlas of Large Galaxies

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Large angular-diameter galaxies occupy a special place in the history of astronomy and continue to play a pivotal role in observational cosmology and in the study of galaxy formation and evolution. So-called “large galaxies,” $>10\text{--}20$ arcsec in angular diameter, are important because they are spatially well-resolved, making it possible to study them in significantly greater detail than more distant galaxies.

In large, nearby galaxies we can study the properties and stellar populations of their disk and spheroidal components as separate, distinct features; identify bars, rings, disk asymmetries, and other dynamical structures; discover and characterize their low surface-brightness features such as stellar streams, tidal tails, and

outer envelopes; unveil faint, low-mass satellites; and more.

Long before their physical nature was known, the study of galaxies, or “spiral nebulae,” began with concerted efforts to catalog them. This work began in 1774 with Charles Messier’s *Catalogue des Nébuleuses et des Amas d’Étoiles*, which included 40 (now-famous) galaxies among a full catalog of 110 objects. Subsequently, building on the naked-eye surveys of William Herschel and his sister Caroline and son John (Herschel 1786, 1864), John Louis Emil Dreyer spent more than two decades assembling the *New General Catalogue of Nebulae and Clusters of Stars* (NGC) and the *Index Catalogues* (IC), a sample of approximately 15,000 Galactic and extragalactic objects whose

Figure 1: Optical mosaic of the galaxy merger NGC 520. This system ranks among the largest and brightest galaxies in the SGA-2020. Credit: J. Moustakas/Siena College; CTIO/NOIRLab/DOE/NSF/AURA

designations are still in widespread use today (Dreyer 1888, 1912).

The NGC, IC, and other early catalogs laid the foundation for several important galaxy atlases published in the second half of the 20th century, including the *Catalogue of Galaxies and of Clusters of Galaxies* (CGCG; Zwicky et al. 1968); the *Uppsala General Catalog of Galaxies* and its Addendum (UGC and UGCA; Nilson 1973, 1974); the *Morphological Catalog of Galaxies* (MCG; Vorontsov-Velyaminov & Krasnogorskaya 1974); the *ESO/Uppsala Survey of the ESO (B) Atlas* (ESO; Lauberts 1982); and the *Principal Galaxies Catalogue* (PGC; Paturel et al. 1989). Eventually, data from these and other catalogs were assembled into the indispensable

Third Reference Catalog of Bright Galaxies (RC3; de Vaucouleurs et al. 1991; Corwin et al. 1994), which has facilitated thousands of wide-ranging scientific investigations.

Building on this rich astronomical and scientific heritage, we have assembled a new digital atlas of large galaxies called the Siena Galaxy Atlas (SGA; Moustakas et al. 2023). The 2020 version of the Atlas, the SGA-2020, includes optical and infrared mosaics of nearly 400,000 galaxies limited to approximately $r = 18$ AB mag and an angular diameter of 25 arcsec; it uses optical (*grz*) imaging from the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI) Legacy Imaging Surveys collected at Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory and Kitt Peak National Observatory, both Programs of NSF’s NOIRLab, and at the University of Arizona’s Steward Observatory (Dey et al. 2019), as well as custom mid-infrared imaging from the unWISE image stacks from Meisner et al. (2021).

The SGA-2020 includes multi-wavelength mosaics (Figures 1 and 2), azimuthally averaged optical surface-brightness profiles (Figure 3), archival metadata, and much more for the full sample of galaxies covering roughly 20,000 sq. deg. (nearly three-quarters of the extragalactic sky, $|b| > 20^\circ$; Figure 4). Notably, for many of the largest (NGC/IC/ Messier) galaxies in the sky, the SGA-2020 delivers the first reliable measurements of the optical positions, shapes, and sizes of large galaxies since the RC3 was published more than 30 years ago.

The SGA-2020 will facilitate a renewed effort to tackle several outstanding problems in extragalactic astrophysics and will support studies of time-domain and multimessenger

Figure 2: Optical mosaics of 42 galaxies from the SGA-2020 sorted by increasing angular diameter from the top left to the bottom right, illustrating the tremendous range of types, sizes, colors, internal structure, and environments of the galaxies in the atlas. The horizontal white bar in the lower left corner of each panel represents 1 arcminute, and the mosaic cutouts range from 3.2 to 13.4 arcminutes.

astronomical events, which are often hampered by incomplete or heterogeneous catalogs of large, nearby galaxies (e.g., Abbott et al. 2020). Moreover, within the 14,000-sq.-deg. DESI footprint, the SGA-2020 is ensuring high photometric completeness for the DESI Bright Galaxy Survey (BGS) and is facilitating high-impact ancillary science through a variety of secondary targeting programs (DESI Collaboration et al. 2023).

Finally, the SGA-2020 will continue to help promote astronomy by engaging the broader public with visually striking color mosaics of large, well-resolved, nearby galaxies, enabling a myriad of educational and public outreach activities.

We expect the SGA-2020 to have lasting legacy value for a wide range of studies of relatively nearby, spatially resolved galaxies. But we do not plan to stop with the SGA-2020. In the next version of the catalog, we intend to incorporate additional Dark Energy Camera (DECam) *i*-band imaging, as well as ultraviolet and infrared imaging (and surface-brightness profiles) from GALEX and unWISE, respectively; to increase the completeness and homogeneity of the sample, particularly in terms of optical surface brightness; to improve the deblending and masking of galaxies around bright stars, in crowded cluster fields, and for close companions (e.g., galaxy mergers); and to incorporate all the available DESI spectroscopy into the final data products. Stay tuned!

Acknowledgments

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Figure 3: Illustration of the key steps and data products of the SGA-2020 for PGC 193192, the second-largest member of the PGC 193199 Group. The three panels on the left-hand side show (top left) a color montage of the optical imaging; (middle left) a color montage of the corresponding model image; and (bottom left) the r-band image with masked pixels zeroed out (white pixel values). The right-hand panels show (top right) the azimuthally averaged g- (blue), r- (green), and z- (red) surface-brightness profiles as a function of the semimajor axis; (middle right) the observed-frame g - r (purple) and r - z (orange) color profiles; and (bottom right) the curve-of-growth of PGC 193192 in g (filled blue squares), r (filled green circles), and z (filled red triangles).

Figure 4: Celestial distribution of the 383,620 galaxies in the SGA-2020 in an equal-area Mollweide projection in equatorial coordinates.